

Paper 7

**IMPLEMENTATION OF THE GREEN TECHNOLOGY
IN THE BUSINESS SECTORS AND ITS ADVERS
EFFECT “SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KARKALA
TALUK”**

Vikas kumar*, Saritha N.*

*1st m.com, ALVAS PG studies and research Centre Moodbidri Mangalore taluk, Karnataka
India

Vikas.k.p69@gmail.com

sarithan791@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Present scenario of the modern technological world .Generation is updating with the tremendous speed. In the same scene we started to destroy the nature also by more paper work this made more burden to people only .This paper mainly concentrate on the implementation of green technology in business sectors and its adverse effect mainly on the small businesses sectors rather than in industry .So study that taken in karkala taluk from the small shop to large shops 150 samples by observing the data collected from the personal interview and secondary data some of the small shop are suffer and are not so well worse of technology some are very use full and some are satisfactory for the Green technology digitalization and demonetarisation act as a fuel to it.With the help this the new phase of the India can be seen in upcoming days. For the efficient and effective implementation can be done by the peoples only .The present scenario and generation is giving the good response to it but every once contribution is needed for the betterment of the new system

INTRODUCTION

The recent emerging issue of demonetarization and digitalization of the economy by the government played a very important role in the economy .it makes a saviour effect on the people on the same time the government going to impose the green technologies to save the environment and make come from all the hurdles. Especially in the business sector the government made the some idea of cash less transactions and in similarly made banking sectors also green sector by the use of paper less so that can save the trees. And the main advantages of the green technology to the government is to adopt the green technology is by

this the government and it sector get the record for all the transitions and difficult to escape from the taxation policy so that it made the peoples to pay the tax compulsory

This will help full to find out the dealings like land dealing vehicles dealing in unauthorised way and it will be come down and other some of the non-bill purchase these will be find out the demonetarisation is the best effective tool to the implementation of the green technology By the implementation GDP of the country will be increased and for the some extent the shadow economy will come down

On the other hand the green technology is says that it saves the environments like in rain water harvesting, transport sector waste management ,energy ,and other sectors of day today use of the technologies

OBJECTIVES

- To study how effective the green technology in business sectors
- To examine who adopted green technology more
- To check the adverse effect of the green technology in business sector

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The relevant data for the study has been collected from both primary and secondary sources. A large part of the analysis is exclusively based on the primary data.

ABOUT GREEN TECNOLOGY

Green Technology is the development of the use of the natural resources more and more instead of using the non-renewable resources more concentration on the renewable resources on the other and the green technology is the reducing of the human work in the all sector reduce the human work and concentrated on the more technology which is eco-friendly in the nature that save the natural resources trees etc.

FOUR PILLARS OF GREEN TECHNOLOGY POLICY

- Energy –get the energy by the natural way without of use of non-renewable resources and more concentrate on the energy get by free of cost or god gift wind,sloar light
- Environment – use of resources in limited way to save for the future generation and awareness about to save the resources and giving idea of the our environment and our pollution level to the peoples
- Economy - use of these green technology for the development of the nation by implementation made in the business sector and it made the track of the all the record of the business's transaction and it made the free flow of the economy and free from frauds
- Social –overall improvement of the society is made with the technology in different sectors ,and our society so advanced and fast development in all the sectors

PRIME MINISTER MAIN STEPS ON GREEN TECHNOLOGY

Ø Honourable Prime Minister Narendra modi called for a paradigm shift in global attitudes towards climate change, from carbon credit towards green credit," it means the

peoples have to go more concentrated for the green credits not only on the environment but also concentrate on the other field

Ø Instead of focusing on the only environment taught and emissions, focus should shift on what we have done for clean energy generation, energy conservation and energy efficiency, and what more can be done in these areas

Ø Careful evaluation of all the initiatives that have been taken by India in areas like solar energy, wind energy, biomass energy, and transportation projects that have reduced distances or travel times and save more energy and lead to the better utilization of natural resources

Ø Have to provide public awareness not only in the local level it have to be on the national level when launching the new green technology

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

TABLE 1:- Green technology knowledge

Interpretation: on the basis of above data we have analysed that, knowing about the green

Contents	Yes %	No %	Some Extent%	None of the above%	Total %
Knowing about green technology	87	0	13	0	100
Green technology is usefully	32	34	34	0	100
Green technology made effect the business sector	42	8	34	16	100

technology 87% knows and 13 for the some extent means all are known about the green technology. Green technology is more use full 32% and 34% no and 34% some extent, the more than 42 % says green technology is very use full and only 8% say no and 34 says for some extent

TABLE 2:- Green technology adopted by entrepreneurs:

Interpretation: on the basis of above data we have analysed that, more than 62% are not adopted and 23% for some extent only the 15% of the peoples are adopted the green technology in their business sectors

Sectors	Using	Not using	Some extent	Total %
Solar panels	20	63	17	100
Rain water harvesting	5	95	0	100
Cards acceptance	54	22	24	100
Waste management	0	100	0	100
Cash less payments made	63	10	27	100
Use of paytem, bhima, etc. apps	40	55	5	100
Transport sector	5	95	0	100

TABLE 3 – Different types of the green technology is using

Interpretation: on the basis of above data we have analysed that, waste management is not done by anyone but the card acceptance and digital use of the format cashless payments are done by the more percentage so that 63, 40, 54% all are supported the use of green technology in the business sectors but the solar panel or solar is not using by the 20% business sector and the rain water

TABLE 4:- Green technology in business sectors:

Content	YES%	NO%	Some Extent%	Total %
Is all green technology is usable	10	58	32	100

The payments are made in e-payments	42	33	25	100
It is too costly to install	84	8	8	100
Green technology is compulsory	84	16	0	100
Technical issues faced while using green technology	34	33	33	100
Not necessary to business sector	12	62	26	100

Interpretation: on the basis of above data we have analysed that, the most of the peoples say the 58% not usable by all the sectors in the business more .the 84% peoples say it is very costly so that it is burden to them but in the same way the peoples will propose to use or make the green technology compulsory in the same case the 62% of the peoples say it is not necessary to the small retail shops and other small small business

SUGGESTIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The green technology is quit harder to install and costlier to adopt in the business sector although the subsidy and scheme are adopted by the government the peoples are not willing to use, the peoples want more about green technology we have install and adopt green technology it must be made compulsory so that we can save energy resources man power for the future generation. The strict rules must imposed on the all the sector of the economy, so that it will lead to the economic development increase the GDP, green technology must be made easy and some of the technical issues are to be reduced .more offers and more advantages must be given to the business peoples to attract towards the green technology

CONCLUSION

In whole area of karkala there is so more percentage of the peoples think that the green technology is not needed to their sector but they were interested to use because of the larger implementation fees and the so many technical issues are also concerned with green technology if it made compulsory may be adopted in their business sector but the peoples are more interested towards energy saving and other saving things like solar, rain water harvesting, for some extent so the green technology is use full to all .but the business sector use it for the financial activity rather than the other activity so that business sector is more not preferred with some of the fields of green technology

BIBLIOGRAPHY

<http://www.krishisanskriti.org>

<http://www.livemint.com>